

EDUCATING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON NATIONAL VALUES

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Abstract: In this article, opinions are expressed about the importance and positive features of educating students and young people with the help of national values in the course of primary education. The role of national values in the educational process will also be discussed.

Key words: Education system, national value, tolerance, educational process, peace-loving, indicator.

Introduction:

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in the book "Humanity, virtue and creativity are the main foundations of our national idea" set the task of educating the young generation based on national values in our modern education process.

National values are a set of qualities, customs and cultural traditions of our people that have been practiced since time immemorial. In this sense, in the process of education, it is necessary to form the following qualities in primary school students:

- valuing a person;
- Loving the country;
- respect others;
- to prioritize the interests of others over one's own interests;
- hard work.

These qualities are embedded in the mentality, that is, the nature of our people. Every family tries to follow them. The main task of a primary school teacher is to instill these qualities in the minds of students. Primary school students should be taught the following customs typical of our people:

- living as a community;
- respect the neighbor;
- sharing goodness;
- selfishness and not taking revenge on wealth;
- live by honest work;
- to be the owner of a profession or trade.

Foreign thinkers also recognize that these customs are compatible with the national nature of our people. For example, the great Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov wrote in his work "Doomsday" that "the customs of the Uzbeks served as Babylon for the Turkic peoples." It is known that the civilization of mankind started from the state called Babylon, which exists in

modern Asia. In other words, humanity has passed from the system of barbarism to the system of humanity.

Primary school students should be introduced to the following cultural lifestyle traditions characteristic of our people:

- always walk cleanly, dress cleanly and observe cleanliness;
- providing material and moral support to the needy;
- to treat others with respect for oneself;
- sharing food with others;
- to treat people the same in good and bad days;
- considering the family sacred.

These traditions not only socialize the minds of students, but also play an important role in the formation of the national spirit in them. Education of elementary school students based on national values is based on these foundations. At the same time, the spirit of respecting the national values of the 130 nationalities and peoples living in our country is instilled in the students. Because the national values of these peoples also correspond to the values of our people.

Instilling universal human values in the minds of primary school students. Consciousness is a set of concepts, thoughts and habits that arise in the brain organ of a person. In this respect, as our pedagogues rightly point out, the minds of elementary school students are like blank white paper. This issue requires the formation of purposeful and relevant values in the minds of 7-11-year-old students. Universal values are also important in this regard.

Universal values are a set of approaches accepted by others after the experience of the peoples living in this world. For this reason, the President recommends paying attention to universal human values in the education of young people.

A. Rubenstein, a Russian pedagogue and psychologist, emphasizes that consciousness consists of the brain, mind and emotions. Therefore, the role of the following universal values is important in the formation of the minds of 7-11-year-old students:

- fraternity;
- love of peace;
- tolerance.

The value of fraternity is a necessity for all peoples, and it expresses the approaches to the present, past and future of each nation. Therefore, in the educational programs of the United Nations, it is noted that the value of universal brotherhood should be learned by the children of every people and nation.

The value of peacefulness occupies an important place in the life of mankind. Therefore, inculcating the value of peace-loving into the mind of a person is one of the primary issues in world Pedagogy. However, in countries that are lagging behind in the development process, instilling the value of peace in the education of young people is slow. For this reason, pedagogic scientists are concerned about the low level of peace-loving skills of young people in countries such as Afghanistan and Syria. In our country, this value is defined as one of the main pillars of education policy.

Tolerance is based on the formation of religious, national and universal ideas in a person. The religious content of tolerance is determined by believing in different religions in

one society. The national content of tolerance is explained by the coexistence of different nations and peoples in one society. The universal content of tolerance consists in mutual friendship and cooperation of all peoples of the world. If these ideas are instilled in the minds of elementary school students, they will be formed as individuals who feel responsible for their society and human life. In general, instilling universal human values into the minds of young people is one of the main directions in Uzbekistan's state policy on education.

Assessment of the level of upbringing of primary school students in the spirit of national and universal values.

The effectiveness of educating primary school students in the spirit of national and universal values is evaluated by the students' preparation for the next stages of education. In the current education system of Uzbekistan, primary school graduates are prepared for the following types of education:

- to secondary general education schools;
- Presidential schools;
- creative schools;
- to specialized schools.

In the process of preparing primary school students for these types of education, it is important that they are brought up in the spirit of national and universal values. Therefore, on the basis of these values, the following indicators for evaluating the level of education can be defined:

- elementary school students' knowledge of national values;
- awareness of universal human values of this category of students;
- students' ability to observe national and universal values;
- students' respect for their nationality and other nationalities.

These indicators determine the level of education of primary school students in the spirit of national and universal values. For this reason, the tasks of the head of the primary school will be expanded, and on the basis of the Law on "Teacher's Status", which is expected to be adopted soon, studying the education level of the primary school students is defined as one of the main tasks of the head of the school.

In pedagogical literature, the concept of "indicator" is used as a term that defines the quality indicator of education and upbringing. In this sense, it is important to pay attention to the indicators, that is, the quality indicator of the level of upbringing in this spirit, in the work of educating primary school students in the spirit of national and universal human values. It should be based on the following:

- the formation of a set of nationalities, customs and manners characteristic of the nature of our people in the student's mind and behavior;
- that universal approaches such as respecting others, not prioritizing personal interests and always being ready to help others, which exist in the culture of our nation, are being formed in the student's morals and moral relations;
- the student's behavior and adaptation to the team are formed in accordance with the discipline and general actions of the team;
- that self-awareness and striving for ideal goals are formed in the student's outlook.

Summary:

All this gives opportunities to educate elementary school students in the spirit of national and universal values based on indicators. Therefore, these basics must be mastered by students in

the process of higher pedagogical education. Formation of worldview, ethics and practical skills of elementary school students through education of national and universal values is considered one of the most important needs of the society

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